

Forest Operational monitoring using Copernicus and UAV hyperSpectral data

Global operational monitoring of changing forest ecosystems

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Forest disturbance

- FAO: 1980-2002, **57 million ha of forest damaged** by biotic agents;
- Europe: 43% of forest land cover;
 - Disturbances in 6.4% of these area (conservative) (22 million m³ of growing stock);
 - **44%** of disturbance due to **biotic agents**;
 - Portugal: 2%+ **GDP** and 100 000+ **jobs**.

Drivers of change

Global Trade & Climate Change

Pinewood Nematode

- Pinewood Nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) is representative of the trend

Maritime pine
(Host tree)

Vector
(*Monochamus galloprovincialis*)

Nematode
(*B. xylophilus*)

Pinewood Nematode: symptoms

- Rapid yellowing / wilting of needles;
- Reduction resin exudation;
- Dried canopy.

Pinewood Nematode: dispersal

Pinewood Nematode: in Europe

- First detected in:
 - Portugal (mainland): 1999
 - Spain: 2008
 - Madeira (Pt): 2009
- Detections in *Pinus pinaster* and *Pinus nigra* (?)

Pinewood Nematode: barriers to containment

- Insufficient **identification** of infested trees;
- Late (or never) **felling** of infested trees;
- Inadequate **transportation** of woody materials;
- Insufficient **awareness** and mitigation strategies.

Pinewood Nematode: climate change

In: Alain Roques et al., Pine wood nematode, pine wilt disease, vector beetle and pine tree: How a multiplayer system could reply to climate change. CAB International 2015, Climate Change and Insect Pests. 220-234.

Project FOCUS

- Horizon 2020 project promoted by 3 European partners for a budget of nearly 2 million euros.

3 pillars:

1. More & better information;
2. Make it accessible;
3. Ensure it is timely.

Project FOCUS: objectives

- Develop new **information products** capable of providing the location of infested trees and other disturbances (stewardship);
- **Algorithms** relying on:
 - Sentinel-2, UAV, and airborne data;
 - Multi- and hyperspectral
- Enhance **Silvisense** digital platform for data distribution and exploration.

Project FOCUS: resources

UAV

SAT

Airborne

Project FOCUS

Test sites in
central Portugal

Project FOCUS: stakeholders

- Strong participation: field, lab, policy, awareness...

Project FOCUS: solutions

- Integrated solution: multiple data sources + 1 platform

Project FOCUS: preliminary results I

- Since January:
- 14 Field Surveys Conducted: thousands of samples collected (and lab analyses);
- 1st UAV survey complete;
- 2nd UAV survey + APEX (airborne) survey this week;
- 1 User Workshop;

Project FOCUS: preliminary results II

Project FOCUS: preliminary results III

- Spectral library of substantial size, covering wide range of plant health status;
- Connected to simultaneous collection of samples for laboratorial analysis: new products.

Project FOCUS: next steps

- “Focus” on algorithm and platform development.

Product delivery: Silvisense

Silvisense: processing massive a volume of data

Silvisense: scalability

- From 10 x 10 m to entire countries: already operational.

Conclusion

- Large number of **local threats**: shared traits or tailored solutions needed?
- Flexible **detection + management** tools required;
- Monitoring of current (or past) ranges is insufficient: **broaden surveillance areas** needed for a rapid response;
- Reinforce the integrated analysis of **biotic and abiotic** variables, using traditional and emerging techniques;
- Avoid information (or data...) **overload**.

Thank you!

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